

Recent R&D of Smart Composites in Japan

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SUMMARY: This paper describes recent studies on smart composites running in Japan. Many researches and developments on smart composites can be seen at Japanese conferences on composite materials. These studies can be categorized into sensing and actuating from the viewpoint of the smart functions. The sensing functions are applied to process monitoring, and health monitoring. On the other hand, the actuation functions are available for vibration damping, noise reduction, high-deformable composites and repair. All of these applications of smart composites are studied in Japan. The functional elements mentioned in this paper are optical fiber sensors, dielectric sensors, piezoelectric materials, shape memory alloy (SMA) and electro-rheological (ER) fluid. Polymer matrix composites (PMC) are mainly addressed as host composite materials, while the smart composites using metal matrix composites (MMC) are also proposed. Researchers in Japanese institutes have focused on the basic researches of smart composites since the early 1990s. In addition, practical studies in Japan have been increasing because it has been recognized that smart composites is a promising technology to reduce the cost, improve the reliability and upgrade the value for a few years. As well as the basic studies in laboratory, the practical studies are addressed in this paper.

KEYWORDS : Smart composites, Japanese R&D review, Sensing and actuation

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have been designed so that they have better properties of weight, stiffness, strength, durability, etc. under the traditional design concept. This design concept is passive, that is, the properties are not controllable in the use. Recently, an active design concept of composite materials using functional elements has come out. Composite materials tailored under this concept are called smart composites. The development of smart composites has begun mainly in United States since the last 1980s. This idea spreads quickly over the world, also in Japan. Researches on smart composites in Japan had been focused just on the basic research mainly by the institutes until several years ago. Today, a technology of smart composites catches attention of Japanese engineering developers because it has been recognized that smart composites technology is a promising one to reduce the cost, to improve the reliability and to upgrade the value.

Smart composites have active functions of sensing and actuation like self-diagnosis, vibration damping, repair and so on. These functions are realized by using functional elements such as optical fiber sensors, dielectric sensors, piezoelectric materials, shape memory alloy (SMA),

electrostrictive materials, magnetostrictive materials, electro-rheological (ER) or magneto rheological (MR) fluids, etc. Some of the reinforcements or matrix used for traditional composites are also reevaluated as functional materials. The targeted composites are principally polymer matrix composites (PMC), while some researchers are interested in metal matrix composites (MMC). The sensing functions of smart composites are available for manufacturing process monitoring and health monitoring. On the other hand, the actuation functions can be applied to vibration damping, noise reduction, deformation and repair.

As well as basic researches in laboratory, many practical researches have also begun since the end 1990s. The smart composites technology tends, actually, to be applied to high-cost composites structures such as civil structures, space structures, aircraft and ships because of the expensive devices and the high-cost manufacturing. The Japanese five years' program of R&D for smart materials and structural system, which has started since FY 1998 with support of NEDO (New Energy and Industrial Technology Development Organization), has triggered the practical researches. This program includes basic researches on smart composites, development of sensor and actuator elements, and development of smart structures. The model structure of aircraft fuselage, which is made of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) and includes sensors and actuators, will be demonstrated in FY 2002. The detail of the demonstration will be presented at the 13th International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM-13), which will be held at Beijing, China in 2001.

The present paper introduces the researches and developments of smart composites advancing in Japan during a few years. The researches are categorized from the viewpoint of the functions, which are sensing and actuation.

SENSING

Smart composites with sensing function have two main targets, which are manufacturing process monitoring and health monitoring. The process monitoring is performed in manufacturing process of composites products. On the other hand, health monitoring provides a self-diagnosis function to composites products in service. Small *in situ* sensors are embedded in composites for monitoring of the internal state. Material state of composites can be also monitored by measuring changes in the micro properties by attached sensors on the composites. Some sensors are available both for the process monitoring and for the health monitoring.

Process Monitoring

The process monitoring is important to compose the optimized control system of molding process of PMC. Especially the cure of thermosetting resins should be monitored to shorten time of the cure cycle or to control the quality. The cure monitoring can be performed by optical fiber sensors, dielectric sensors and piezoelectric sensors. Mainly four types of optical fiber sensors, spectroscopy-based sensors, refractive index sensors, strain sensors and temperature sensors are available for the cure monitoring. Spectroscopy-based sensors measure the changes in chemical structure of resins or curing agents. Refractive index sensors measure refractive index of resins in the cure process. Strain and temperature sensors are available for

monitoring of the cure reaction and the residual strain in the molding process. In Japan, strain and temperature fiberoptic sensors have been mainly studied for the cure process monitoring.

The strain in molding process were monitored by two kinds of strain sensors of embedded extrinsic Fabry-Perot interferometric (EFPI) sensors and fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors [1-3]. This strain monitoring was applied to autoclave molding [1], filament winding (FW) molding [2] and RTM molding [3]. These experimental results proved that the embedded EFPI sensors could measure the curing shrink as well as the thermal shrink. Therefore, it can be said that EFPI strain sensors can monitor the cure reaction as well as the thermal residual strain. On the other hand, it was found to be difficult for FBG sensor to monitor the cure reaction quantitatively because the strain resolution of embedded FBG sensors was not enough to measure the curing shrink. However the results of the strain measurement by the embedded FBG sensors in RTM molding showed that the FBG sensors represented good performance to monitor the thermal shrink [1].

Dielectric sensing is a popular method for *in situ* cure monitoring of composite materials. The embedding of dielectric sensors becomes possible by development of miniaturized dielectric sensors. The distributed sensing techniques by the embeddable dielectric sensors were proposed [4]. It was proved that this sensor could be used also to detect flow front of the liquid resin in the injection process [4]. It was also shown that distribution of dielectric properties could be monitored by using high-frequency electric waves with time domain reflectometry (TDR) [5].

Piezoelectric wafers can monitor elasticity and viscosity of composites indirectly from the frequency response of the wafers, which compose an electro-mechanical circuit with the resin. The impedance measurement by the embedded piezoelectric wafers was applied to cure monitoring of composite laminates in autoclave molding [6].

Health Monitoring

Optical fiber sensors are powerful sensors for the *in situ* measurement of strain and temperature to monitor whether products is in the safe environment. The strain sensors, which are employed for the cure monitoring in the fabrication, can also be used in service. It was shown that the internal strain in FW pipes could be measured precisely by using the embedded EFPI sensors [2]. The embedded FBG sensors in RTM molded composites showed good performance of strain measurement on the cyclic loading tests [3]. Small-diameter (40 μ m) optical fibers were developed to embed the optical fibers in composites materials easily [7]. It was reported that the small-diameter FBG fiberoptic sensors embedded in CFRP skin of sandwich panels of satellite structures could monitor strain in a space chamber [8]. Since interferometric fiberoptic sensors are effective for high-speed measurement of strain, they are applied to measurement of dynamic strain in composites. The strain measurement of composite laminates using Michelson interferometric fiberoptic sensors were conducted [9]. Brillouin optical time domain reflectometric (B-OTDR) sensing system is suited for measurement of strain distribution in large composite structures due the long length resolution. It was reported that the combined sensor system between B-OTDR and FBG sensor system in a single optical fi-

ber had an ability of simultaneous measurement of strain and temperature [10]. A B-OTDR fiberoptic sensor system was applied to health monitoring of the composites hull of the racing yacht. It was reported that the strain distribution was successfully monitored at the inspections after the races [11].

On the other hand, damage monitoring has been a hot topic in a field of composite materials. Since the small damages such as matrix cracks and debondings are too small to be detected by quick inspections, composites are used in the range of the low strength where these damages do not occur. Therefore, damage tolerance design, which allows such unserious damages, is very important for us to use composites in the wide range of the strength. However, some ways of the health assurance has been required for the application of damage tolerance design to real structures in conservative area like aviation. The real-time damage monitoring is an attractive method to assure the health of the composite structures. Optical fiber sensors, optical sensing, and electrical resistance measurement can catch the damage initiation directly and modal analyses of composite structures can monitor damages indirectly using analysis models.

The break sensors using optical fibers are simplest and cheapest sensors for damage detection. The optical power loss tells us the damage initiation when the embedded optical fibers are broken by the crossing cracks [12]. This sensing technique can be regarded as the final function of optical fiber sensors. The microbend sensors also depend on the optical power loss, while the loss is caused by the local deformation of the optical fibers. It was reported that the plastic optical fibers could detect the transverse cracks in cross-ply CFRP laminates [13]. It was also proved that multi-mode optical fibers were available for detection of damages in GFRP laminates [14]. The monitoring of impact response on the stiffened CFRP panels for airplane structures was conducted by using the embedded small-diameter optical fibers. It was shown that the optical power loss indicates the impact signal, and the optical power was recovered after the impact when no damage occurred [15]. The other method of the direct detection of the internal damages using optical fiber sensors is the spectra monitoring of embedded FBG sensors. General FBG sensors are easily affected by non-uniform strain distributed along the gauge length of about 10 mm. Then the embedded FBG sensors can catch the non-uniform strain distribution induced by damages. The observation of the transverse cracks in cross-ply CFRP laminates was conducted by using FBG sensors embedded in the 0° plies adjacent to the 90° plies [16].

Optical transmission sensing is effective for detection of damages in transparent composites like GFRP. The health monitoring system of composites laminate using an EL backlight was proposed. It was shown that the optical power of the light transmitted in composite laminates decreases with the internal damages increase [17]. The health monitoring technique using transmitted light through FRP was used to detect defects in the alumina-FRP load-support structures, which support a superconducting coil vessel of a linear-motor train in Japan [18].

Since electrical properties of the composites reinforced with conductive reinforcements involve strain and damage information, the measurement of electrical properties has been ex-

pected as the method of a real-time non-destructive evaluation. The advantage of this method is no need of sensors inside of materials. It was shown that the electrical resistance of CFRP laminates changed with strain and recorded damages progress of fiber breaks and matrix cracks under fatigue load [19]. The smart FRP patches reinforced with carbon particles were developed for measurement and record of strain under fatigue load [20]. It was reported that size and location of delaminations in CFRP laminates could be detected by using electrical potential method with multiple electrodes [21]. The measurement of electrical resistivity oxidized nickel fibers in aluminum matrix-based composites was conducted to monitor temperature and strain [22].

The damages of composite materials change macro properties and thereby they change the modal shapes and frequency. Therefore, the changes in the dynamic response of the vibrated composites reflect initiation and development of the damages. In this method, the active systems using a combination between actuators and sensors are better than the passive systems using only sensors, because the active systems are available for a detection of the static damages as well as the impact damages. Piezoelectric films are good for the purpose due to the light weight and the function of actuation. The analysis methods are also important to know the kind, size and position of the damages. The health monitoring system using response surface methodology was proposed for an identification of size and location of delaminations in FRP laminates [23]. The identification method of size and location of delaminations in symmetrical laminated plates using a frequency response function approach was proposed [24]. Localized flexibility method was applied to internal damage detection of CFRP laminates [25] and CFRP composite pipes [26].

ACTUATION

Smart composites with actuation function have four main targets, which are vibration damping, noise reduction, high-deformable composites and repair. Several actuator elements, which are piezoelectrics, SMA, ER-fluid, have been applied to improve damping properties of composite materials. Methods of material damping can be used for reduction of the noise caused by vibration of composites panels. High-deformable composites propose hingeless structures such as flapless wings. The laminated actuators using difference of coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) among laminas were categorized into high-deformable composites in this paper. The repair of composites is a very serious theme because the micro cracks in the matrix or on the interface degrades the performance of composites. Improvement of damage resistivity of composites can be achieved by employing high-power actuators.

Vibration Damping and Noise Reduction

The many ideas to improve vibration damping properties of composite structures have been proposed. These ideas can be categorized into passive damping and active damping. Under the design concept of the passive damping, damping components is configured so that the composite structural system has best damping properties in the specific frequency range. The structures designed under the concept need no power source to activate dampers. On the contrary, the active damping is a concept to control damping properties of structures using pow-

ered actuators. Since the structures possessing active damping functions have good damping properties in wide frequency range, it can be apply to the structures, which may suffer unexpected vibration. From the viewpoint of damping components, the damping of composite structures has two concepts of structural system damping and material damping. The concept of structural system damping employs dampers as structural members to dissipate vibration energy in the total system. In the concept, composites members are not expected as high-damping materials. On the other hand, the damping properties of composite members should be optimized in the method of the material damping. In this paper, the material damping using actuators is focused.

Piezoelectric ceramics (PZT), piezoelectric polymers (PVDF), ER-fluid and SMA can be used for the material damping. These actuator elements, which have shapes of film or fiber, are attached on or embedded in composites. It was reported that interleaved CFRP laminates using bonded PZT sheet was effective for passive damping of the vibration [27]. The hybrid system between the embedded PZT films and the sandwiched ER-fluid between CFRP laminates was proposed with new optimal control system [28, 29]. The experimental and theoretical results represented that the hybrid system could provide good damping properties. The active damping using damping layers, which were composed with CFRP laminates and sealed ER-fluid, was conducted. The outside CFRP skins worked as constrained layer and the inside skins, as electrodes. It was reported that the damping property could be controlled by applying electric field [30, 31]. It was shown that CFRP laminates, which are designed under the passive damping concept using embedded SMA wires, had good performance of damping [32].

The noise reduction is an application of vibration control of materials. However, the different control system from the material damping should be required since the vibration modes are different from the acoustic power modes. The analytical modeling of the acoustic power modes generated by vibration of composite laminates was proposed [33]. It was described that the control of the noise from composite panels was successfully conducted by using attached piezoceramics on the panels [34].

High-Deformable Composites

High-deformable composites driven by high-displacement actuators are desired to have low bending stiffness. Therefore, this technology is suited for thin composite beams or skins. The vibration and shape control of the cantilever beam structures using distributed PZT and PVDF has been demonstrated. It was reported that the technology could be applied to control of the flexile structure of a satellite antenna [35].

Several unique ideas using high-deformable composite materials have been proposed for actuators. It was shown that the actuators composed with CFRP laminates and metal plates can be tailored to express the high deformation by the electrical resistance heating. It was described that the laminated actuator could be tuned by setting the transverse CTE to the metal value so that the actuator could move in plane. The metal matrix actuators reinforced by SiC fibers were also proposed as high-temperature actuators [36].

Repair and Improvement of Damage Resistivity

Micro damages are the first damage mode occurring in composite materials. Although the micro damages are not fatal, they degrade stiffness or damage resistance of composites. Since the micro damages are distributed inside of composites, it is difficult to repair the damages. To minimize the effect of such damages on the material performance, two approaches using actuators can be seen in Japan. One is an improvement of the damage resistivity and another is a repair of the damages. Since the load level of initiation of the micro damages depends on the residual stress in the fabrication of composites, SMA actuators can be used to reduce the residual stress to delay or suppress the damages. It was reported that the SMA wires, which were embedded in the 0° plies of CFRP cross-ply laminates, delay transverse cracks in the 90° plies [37]. It was proved that the SMA foil, which was embedded between the 0° ply and the 90° ply of CFRP cross-ply laminates, was useful to delay and suppress transverse cracks in the 90° plies [38].

Internal damages distributed in materials can be repaired by filling the voids with the heated and melted materials if the materials keep the properties after the repair process. Therefore, the micro damages in thermoplastic PMC can be repaired, while it is generally impossible to repair such damages in thermosetting PMC. However, a new idea of repair of thermosetting PMC by using melting plastic particles mixed in the matrix as actuator, was proposed. It was demonstrated that thermosetting polymer matrix composites mixed with thermoplastic polymer particles or uncured thermosetting polymer particles had ability of repair by heating them [39].

CONCLUSIONS

As introduced in this paper, many researches and developments on smart composites are running in Japan. We can also find sessions of smart composites at mot of Japanese conferences on composite materials. Therefore, it can be said that smart composites successfully attract the attentions of many composites researches and developers in Japan. Most of the studies are, however, just feasibility ones because there are many problems enumerated as follows.

1. The design method of smart composites tailored to purpose should be developed.
2. The manufacturing method without skillful labors should be developed.
3. The mechanical properties in severe environment should be cleared.
4. Cost of the active elements should be reduced.

It is expected that these hurdles to the practical application will be jumped by cooperative of researchers in institutes and industries not only in Japan but also in the world.

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